

Paper 1

STUDENT GRADING IN HIGHER EDUCATION FOR COMPETENCY BASED EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Abstract:

Higher Education aims to produce quality professionals who would be economically productive and contribute to the society. Here comes the question how fit are they? Are our passing out graduates ready to take up and perform jobs successfully? Is the present education equipping them for that? What should be the assessment of a graduate be based on? Higher education aims to impart competency to the learners and generally the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired desired level of competence. Examination and assessment are a key indicator for measuring performance of a graduate in the existing credit based education system. The credit based system in higher education is founded on the assumption that grades which a student has secured by way of assessment and evaluation speak what a student has earned by way of education. But the question is how to measure the competency among the graduates who pass out. Various indicators are available in competency based education system (CBES), most important among them is employability. Employability is the capacity to take up and perform job independently with relative ease, although this is something that is usually subject to decision of the employer and therefore difficult to set a bench mark. Our competency measurement model suggests various performance indicators which could directly give a quantifiable idea to judge how successful a person would be in a given job. This paper attempts to outline the major factors contributing to competency, their objectives and outcome. An attempt has also been made to identify such factors which contribute to predict performance in a job situation by judging competency level performance indicators. The interventional strategies for higher education institution is also outlined here.

Keywords : CBES, Competency based education, Outcome based education, Performance level, Competency Measurement model, Competency Measurement Scales.

1. INTRODUCTION :

The higher education has an objective to develop systematic thinking ability of the students by means of enhancing knowledge, skills, and experience which in turn expected to increase the confidence of the solving problems of self and society [1]. In the process of imparting higher education, two models are considered to be relevant in the current century which are (1) Conventional classroom based education model [2-4] and (2) Technology supported online ubiquitous education model [5, 6, 7]. The two higher education systems which are

expected to be attractive to the learners are Choice Based Credit system (CBCS) and Competency based Education system (CBES) [8].

Presently Indian higher education system follows choice based credit system of assessment and evaluation. A credit system is a systematic way of describing an educational programme by attaching credits to its components. The credits in higher education systems may be based on different parameters, such as student workload, learning outcomes and contact hours. University Grants Commission has come up with the Choice Based Credit System (CBCS), a programme in which the students while choosing the prescribed course, which is the core, can opt for any elective or minor or soft skill courses and the entire assessment is graded, based on a credit system. The CBCS provides choice for students to select the elective components in any other institution as well.

Competency-Based Education System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model. It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment. Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution. A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content [6, 8]. This model allows students to work and learn anywhere and as per the curriculum of the University/Higher education institution where they enrolled for their courses have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is most challenging and there is no hard and fast method as well as the rating scale accepted by universally exists today. Competency based education system is not a new concept and is under discussion since 1970 [10-17]. Due to the limitations involved in the evaluation and distribution of scores/ rating of outcomes, CBES model in higher education could not become popular and not adopted in most of the universities.

2. Objectives of the Paper :

This conceptual paper based on explorative research has the following objectives :

- (1) To analyse the distinctive features of competency based education system CBES.
- (2) To study the factors which contribute to competency based education and measuring their performance outcome.
- (3) To discuss Advantages, Benefits, Constraints, and Disadvantages of both CBES and its competency rating scale.
- (4) Challenges in offering CBES as outcome based education system.

3. Features of Competency Based Education System (CBES) :

Competence means ability or capability and performance is the proof of competence. The objective of higher education is to impart competency to the learners and the presumption is that those who undergo higher education have acquired competency. As opposed to this, is the credit based system where the grades directly speak what a student has earned through

education?. But the question is how to measure competency among the graduates who want to pass out. However, this is something that is decided by the employer and difficult to set a benchmark at university level during evaluation for offering graduation certificate. In this paper, we have proposed two grading methods based on a modified 1-10 rating scale and the other is a modified Likert scale model to measure and express competency of a graduate in a given subject/area. In its final form, the Likert Scale is a five or seven-point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on the Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged.

CBES involves educating a student in order to improve the competency of performance in one or more fields of specializations. This includes enhancing his knowledge, skills, and experience along with ethical aspects of doing things systematically to the expectations of the industry. The evaluation of competency should focus on developing the progress report of the candidate periodically to report the speed of learning and achieving the different levels of competency. Such an evaluation process and outcome is called competency rating and reporting. The distinctive features of CBES are :

- (1) Competency based education system focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) It provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) Competency-based programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) It allows students to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) A student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses to be taught by approved faculty members. Instead, in CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) The system allows a student to choose any number of areas where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

4. PERFORMANCE LEVEL MEASUREMENT IN CBES :

Competency based education system focus on developing working skills on a particular set of jobs during a time frame. Those working skills together called as competency comprises of wide ranging skills and expertise mixed with attitude conducive to perform the job adequately and satisfactorily. Various teaching-learning methods including classroom teaching, laboratory based learning, experiential learning, experimental learning, online

learning, internship based projects, fieldwork practicum etc. are adopted to realize the goal in competency based education system. These methods are geared to provide the right opportunity to the student to develop these competencies. Major factors that contribute to build the competency has been identified and classified. Our competency measurement model suggests that what counts on employability are a sum total of outcomes achieved through a set of identifiable factors which has clear objectives and verifiable indicators. The following table (Table 1) list out areas of competency, their performance objective and outcome. The performance indicators suggested against each of this give a clear idea on the expected traits required for employability.

Table 1 : Factors which contributes to competency and their expected performance outcome.

Sl. No.	Areas of Competency	Performance Objective	Performance Outcome	Performance Indicator
1	Communication and comprehension	Translating Thoughts	Rapid Action	Speed
2	Proficiency in writing	Transmitting Ideas	Quick response	Accuracy
3	Generation of new ideas	Trying out new and easier ways	Innovation	Productive efficiency
4	Preserving a vision in life	Commitment to goals	Adaptability	Value addition
5	Desire for learning	Improvement in life	Job meaningful	Pro-activeness
6	Attitude towards life	Combine personal ambitions with employment goals	Positive energy	Positive view
7	Respect for fellow-beings	Accept others contribution	Increased co-operation	Receptiveness
8	Self-control	Strength and determination	Courage in action	Accountability
9	Self confidence	Faith in one's own action	Sustained interest	Quality in work
10	Creativity	Ability to make things happen	Gogetter	More output

Various rating scales have been used in the past to measure intangible quantities like attitude, feelings, quantities, perception, love, affection, happiness, pain, satisfaction, status, talent, knowledge, etc. Most popular among them is the Likert Scale [18]. In higher education institutions competency measurement becomes more relevant than credit grading and calls for the need to evolve measurement parameters relevant to the indicators. A modified Likert Scale Model could be used for this purpose (Table 2). This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given area to a greater extent in a very systematic way. This scale is a 10 point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level.

Table 2 : Competency rating model in a given skill based on 1-10 rating scale

Sl. No.	Competency Grading Level	Grade Point
1	Outstanding	10
2	Excellent	9
3	Very good	8
4	Good	7
5	Above Average	6
6	Average	5
7	Below Average	4
8	Weak	3
9	Very Weak	2
10	Extremely Weak	1

5. GRADING IN COMPETENCY BASED SYSTEM :

This could be a useful tool for the employer to predict the success of a new employee when he is admitted into a new job. For the educational institution it is a reference point to sharpen its interventional strategy to build capability in the new pass-out. It is safely presumed that a person who obtains a minimum of 50% in aggregate and separately in each of these 9 components would perform satisfactorily. Higher score is reflective of the merit of the candidate (Table 3).

Table 3 : Measurable parameters for competency assessment

Sl.No.	Performance Outcome	Operational Indicators	Measureable parameters
1	Rapid action	Speed	Follow deadlines
2	Quick response	Accuracy	Fewer mistakes
3	Innovation	Productive efficiency	Better planning
4	Adaptability	Value addition	Exceeding limitations
5	Job meaningful	Pro-activeness	More output
6	Positive energy	Positive views	Demonstrate initiative
7	Increased cooperation	Receptiveness	Maintaining enthusiasm
8	Courage in action	Accountability	Readiness to follow directions
9	Sustained interest	Self-motivation	Appropriate actions
10	Ability to make things happen	Gogetter	Turns challenges into opportunities

6. MODELS FOR COMPETENCY GRADING SYSTEM :

6.1 Model 1 for Competency Reporting:

This model is based in 1-10 rating scale. This is an extension of choice based credit system grading. Here, the competency level of a student under evaluation is graded using grade points anywhere between one to ten. Absent to evaluation process by the respective student is graded as zero. Depending on evaluator’s assessment on a candidate, grading level and corresponding grading point should be determined. Table 3 lists various competency levels and the corresponding grade points.

6.2 Model 2 for Competency Reporting:

Even if competency is an intangible property, it can be measurable to some extent through various traits. To measure the competency of a graduate in any area/field, we propose another model which is a modified Likert scale model. This scale or metric supports to measure and express the competency of a graduate in a given subject/area to a greater extent in a systematic way. In its final form, this scale is a seven point scale depending on the rigorousness of the evaluation which is used to allow the evaluator to express how much they agree or disagree with a particular statement related to competency level. Based on this modified Likert scale competency indicator, the employability, i.e., the capability to take-up and performs a job by a graduate under consideration with little of support from other members of the organization can be judged. This model is based on 7 point Likert Scale. Here, seven grades are allotted based on a student’s competency on a given skill or subject. The evaluator, through demonstration, shall decide the competency level and fix it to any deserved level and the grade points should be allotted accordingly. In this model, the competency reporting system may follow either optimistic assessment by using positive scale, a most likely assessment scale called neutral scale, or a pessimistic assessment model by using negative scale.

(1) Positive Scale :

This is an optimistic /positive assessment scale used to measure and report the strength of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(2) Neutral Scale :

This is a neutral most-likely assessment scale used to measure and report the abilities of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

(3) Negative Scale :

This is a negative assessment scale used to measure and report the weakness of the candidate in a given competency assessment system.

6.3 Complete Performance Measurement Model based on above Scales :

The competency based performance measurement format consists of listing of various skills required to perform a job satisfactorily and the competency grading level of a candidate along with corresponding grade point. This also includes the time taken by the candidate to reach the required competent level as shown in Competency Report format given in table 4. An example of competency report format shown in table 4 based on positive scale for Accounting job is shown in table 5.

Table 5 : Example of competency report based on positive scale for Accounting job

Name : Ashok B.		Roll No. : 2019K29		DOB:04/04'1999
S.No.	Skills Required for the Job	Competency Grading level	Grade Point	Time taken to reach the level
1	Knowledge	Very good	5	12 months
2	Working skills	Good	4	18 months
3	Expertise level	Excellent	6	12 months
4	Communication	Average	2	08 months
5	Proficiency in writing	Very good	5	18 months
6	Generation of new ideas	Excellent	6	18 months
7	Preserving a vision in life	Average	2	24 months
8	Desire for learning and improvement in life	Excellent	6	12 months

9	Attitude towards life	Average	2	18 months
10	Respect for fellow-beings	Below Average	1	18 months
11	Self-control	Good	4	12 months

7. ABCD OF CBES AND ITS RATING SCALE :

Out of many analysis frameworks developed to analyse a system, concept, ideas, models, or strategies, ABCD analysis framework is an effective and simple framework which analyse the usage of the system/model, factors affecting the system/model, and deep insight into the system/model through identifying critical constitutional elements (elemental analysis) [19-22]. The variation in ABCD analysis called ABCD listing is a qualitative discussion method. ABCD listing consists of listing of advantages, benefits, constraints, and disadvantages of the usage of the system/model [23-39]. In this section, the advantages, benefits, constraints, and Disadvantages of CBES and its rating system developed are listed :

7.1 Advantages :

- (1) CBES focus on building and measuring some pre-defined competency for a student in performing a specified task efficiently and effectively.
- (2) CBES provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education by means of providing a proper direction while choosing the subjects, and in the assessment.
- (3) CBES allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit.
- (4) In this system, a student can progress in his own pace, while improving knowledge, skills, and experience as per the demands of the industry to the extent decided by the institution.
- (5) In CBES, a student has to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content.
- (6) In CBES, a student can choose any number of subjects where he/she is interested to enhance the skills required to do a particular job with learned required competency.

7.2. Benefits :

- (1) The competency of a student is measured in some quantifiable terms.
- (2) The competency scores provided by this evaluation system gives idea to the employers to judge the capability of a graduate while appointing for a job.
- (3) Since CBES provides an opportunity to personalize the learning in higher education, the students can pursue their education in their own plan & pace.
- (4) CBES provides an opportunity to the learner to continue his education while working for a job.
- (5) Based on scored academic credit, a students’ knowledge and skills in doing a particular job can be determined.
- (6) CBES system and its evaluation model do not allow promoting unemployable graduate.
- (7) CBES system allows a student to take any number of subjects so that one can differentiate himself in academic process along with opportunity to become multi-subject specialist.

7.3 Constraints :

- (1) CBES implementation constraints
- (2) CBES Evaluation timeframe constraints
- (3) CBES curriculum constraints
- (4) Lifelong Continuous improvements required based on environmental changes
- (5) Educators mental block for changing the CBCS to CBES

7.4 Disadvantages :

- (1) Since CBES is mainly skill based education system and hence students are deprived to acquire to general education related to a special area.
- (2) The CBES model is focussed model so that the advantages of STEM/STEAM models are not incorporated.
- (3) Student is allowed to become expert on one or related area in order to get required level of competency so that he may become obsolete soon due to changes in environmental conditions like change in technology.
- (4) Adopting new system and training faculty members for new evaluation system is difficult.

8. CHALLENGES OF MEASURING COMPETENCY OF GRADUATES USING ABOVE MODEL :

Based on the proposed model one can measure the skill levels of a student on positive or negative grading scale. Some of the challenges CBES while implementing and evaluation are as follows :

- (1) The competency level in a specific skill for a job can be represented by offering an appropriate grade and corresponding score by the University evaluator so that it can be considered in industry while offering the job.
- (2) The model based on one to ten levels of competency looks straight forward but there are many implementation constraints for the evaluators as well as the industry job interviewers.
- (3) The process of evaluation of competency in a given skill or in an identified job needs experts in that job. Hence the evaluator's team should comprise of both academicians and industry experts. This makes customization of even evaluation process which leads to complex and time consuming process.
- (4) CBES is suitable for honours degrees both in under-graduation (UG) and post-graduation (PG) levels to measure the additional skills imparted during the training period where as it is not practical for pass degrees in UG and PG levels of higher education.
- (5) This model is more suitable for further studies for continuous of education while working in industries instead of students of formal continuous education system.

9. CONCLUSION :

Competency-Based Education System (CBES) is a significant improvement in CBCS model due to the fact that it provides an opportunity to customize and personalize the learning process. CBES in higher education provides a proper direction of required skills to be developed by a student while choosing the subjects, and the assessment. Competency-based education programs allow students to demonstrate academic competence through a combination of assessment and documentation of experience to gain academic credit. In this system, students have to progress at their own pace, incorporates the process of prior learning assessment, and offers a logical framework for improving knowledge, skills and experience. CBES is a continuous improvement program for individuals and as per the demands of the industry. Since a student need not necessarily have to take predetermined required and elective courses, but to demonstrate a defined set of proficiencies and mastery of knowledge and content. Hence the model allows students to work and learn anywhere and have to develop specific competency levels and get a graduation certificate. The evaluation part of Competency based education system is discussed in this paper and an appropriate solution of grading model based on developed competency is proposed.

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